

PLAN-B

Tackling light and noise pollution

Quantifying noise pollution
exposure at the regional scale
within Europe's natural areas

Noise pollution mapping with underpinning methodology

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List of Acronyms

SPL	Sound Pressure Level
Lden	Day-evening-night equivalent SPL as used as a main environmental noise indicator for human centric noise mapping
HP2P	Harmonoise Point-to-Point sound propagation model
HT	Hearing Threshold
HPC	High-performance computing
CNOSSOS	Common Noise Assessment Methods in Europe
ERA5	Fifth generation ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) reanalysis for the global climate and weather
END	Environmental Noise Directive

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the methodology developed to assess environmental noise exposure across European natural areas. The work addresses a major scientific and technical challenge: unlike many environmental pressures, noise cannot be directly observed at continental scale and must therefore be estimated entirely through numerical modelling.

A key challenge is the accurate simulation of sound propagation in natural environments. Receivers are often located close to the ground, where terrain, porous natural surfaces and meteorological conditions strongly influence sound levels. Common large-scale noise mapping approaches, such as ISO 9613-2 and CNOSSOS-EU, do not adequately capture these near-ground propagation effects as was shown by a complex road traffic noise validation study. To achieve the necessary physical realism, the HP2P propagation model was adopted. Acoustic ground properties were derived and parameterized from the Dynamic World dataset using a 3-parameter ground impedance model, while meteorological refraction effects were incorporated using the ERA5 atmospheric data.

Road traffic was identified as the dominant and most consistently mappable environmental noise source across Europe. However, harmonised traffic data are unavailable on a continental scale. To address this limitation, an automated framework was developed that derives traffic-related source characteristics from openly available road network data (Open Street Maps), including road category, number of lanes, and the network connectivity indicator "edge betweenness". Wind turbine noise was also modelled deterministically using turbine location data, a typical source power spectrum during operation, and site-specific meteorological conditions derived from ERA5.

The unprecedented geographical scope of this work creates substantial computational challenges. High-resolution deterministic simulations across all Natura 2000 areas are not feasible, even with advanced computing resources. Therefore, approximately 5,000 1-km² of representative areas were simulated explicitly using the HP2P modelling framework on HPCs. These maps were then subsequently used to train a machine learning model. The learning task was formulated as image-to-image regression, with a U-Net convolutional neural network predicting frequency-resolved sound pressure levels from terrain, land cover, and source characteristics. This approach enables efficient estimation of road traffic noise exposure throughout Natura 2000 areas across Europe while retaining the physical realism of the deterministic simulations.

The methodology produces detailed frequency-resolved noise maps at receiver heights of 0.5 m, 5 m, and 50 m, allowing assessment of noise exposure for both terrestrial and aerial species. Because the underlying maps are generated in the detail of one-third octave bands, species-specific bio-weighted exposure maps can be derived based on communication frequencies and typical receiver heights, providing a more ecologically relevant assessment of potential impacts. Large differences in exposure between species are found in some example areas, easily exceeding 20 dB in exposure.

To complement these high-resolution products, an additional mapping approach was developed using environmental noise maps reported by Member States under the Environmental Noise Directive (END). These maps provide complete European coverage and account for major road,

railway, airport, and industrial noise sources. Recognizing that the END maps were primarily developed for assessing human exposure rather than biodiversity impacts, a conservative binary methodology was adopted. Areas enclosed by the 55 dB Lden contour were classified as significantly noise-exposed, while areas below this threshold were considered non-significantly exposed. By intersecting these contours with natural and semi-natural land cover, a species-relevant exposure indicator was derived, expressing for each 500 m grid cell the fraction of natural habitat exposed to *significant* environmental noise. This approach enables robust large-scale biodiversity analyses while avoiding over-interpretation of the underlying END data.

In summary, the project delivers four complementary noise mapping products and frameworks : (1) deterministic high-resolution road traffic noise maps for selected case-study areas, (2) machine learning-based road traffic noise maps covering Natura 2000 sites across the whole of Europe, (3) deterministic wind turbine noise maps at continental scale for each registered turbine, and in addition, (4) END-based binary exposure maps providing a practical means to assess broader environmental noise exposures from railway, air traffic and industrial sources. Together, these datasets establish a robust foundation for evaluating the impacts of anthropogenic noise on European biodiversity.

1. Introduction

In contrast to nighttime light pollution mapping—largely based on processed satellite imagery—mapping anthropogenic noise across Europe’s natural areas presents a far greater challenge. Noise cannot be directly observed and must instead be fully simulated numerically, introducing substantial methodological and computational complexity.

A first challenge lies in accurately modelling sound propagation in natural environments. Receivers are often located close to the ground, where strong ground effects—particularly over porous surfaces—can significantly alter sound levels. Widely used largescale methods such as ISO 96132 and CNOSSOS-EU are not designed to capture these near ground and terrain related processes in sufficient detail. Applying them uniformly across heterogeneous natural landscapes would therefore risk limited physical realism.

Second, while multiple sound sources contribute to environmental noise exposure, only a subset can be reliably modelled at continental scale. Within the EU, road traffic is by far the dominant source and is therefore the primary focus of this work. However, harmonised and sufficiently detailed traffic data across Europe are lacking. To address this, an automated mapping framework is developed based on publicly available road network data, including road categorisation, enabling consistent large-scale modelling that also accounts for smaller roads.

Third, the geographical scope is unprecedented. Even when restricting the analysis to Natura 2000 sites, the spatial extent remains vast, leading to significant computational constraints. Fully deterministic, high-resolution modelling across all areas is not feasible within realistic resource limits, including the use of supercomputers. To overcome this, a hybrid approach is adopted: detailed simulations are conducted for a representative subset of areas and used to train a machine learning model that can efficiently approximate noise exposure at continental scale.

Environmental noise in natural areas is not limited to road traffic. Sources such as wind turbines and mining activities can also be relevant, particularly in otherwise quiet regions. Wind turbines, for example, are often located in remote areas and can be reasonably modelled as point sources using available location data and typical emission spectra. Mining activities may also generate high local exposure. However, these sources are extremely difficult to predict consistently at European scale due to uncertainties in operational status, temporal variability, and site-specific characteristics.

In practice, mapping is therefore restricted to sources for which predictive modelling is feasible and for which basic input data are available. Additional contributors such as railways, air traffic, and industrial noise are incorporated using noise maps reported by Member States under the Environmental Noise Directive (END). For these sources, large-scale predictive modelling is less reliable—for example due to highly variable railway usage or the complexity of aircraft movement data—making reliance on these reported maps a pragmatic choice. This avoids extensive data reconstruction but comes at the cost of reduced modelling detail and less accurate representation of propagation physics compared to the approach used for road traffic.

Despite these simplifications, developing accurate road traffic noise maps using only open access data while retaining physically meaningful propagation modelling remains highly challenging and resource intensive. Therefore, as a fast-track solution to support initial analyses—such as linking noise exposure to species abundance—EU wide END noise maps are also used to produce an alternative, lower resolution estimate of noise exposure. In the latter, road, railway, airport and industry noise are included as well.

In summary (see Table 1), this deliverable reports on the methodologies to produce two types of noise maps. A first type are highly detailed ones focussing on Natura 2000 areas, forming the basis for detailed environmental impact assessment, for two major sound source types (namely road traffic and wind turbines). Secondly, the noise maps basically relying on the END maps cover more environmental noise sources but come at a much lower spatial detail and physical sound propagation accuracy. The latter, however, can be more readily used for large-scale studies linking anthropogenic noise and species abundance (see WP2.3) all over Europe.

Table 1: Sound sources considered, their spatial coverage, modelling approaches and minimum levels covered.

Sound source	Spatial coverage	Modelling	Minimum level	Comment
Road traffic noise	Natura 2000 zones in Europe	Road categorization and detailed HP2P sound propagation modelling. Main and small(er) roads included.	Not limited	To deploy all over Europe, a surrogate model based on machine learning was used after training on deterministically calculated maps.
Wind turbine noise	Natura 2000 zones in Europe	Typical source power spectrum and detailed HP2P sound propagation modelling.	Not limited	
Road traffic noise	Near major highways outside cities and main roads inside cities	Member state vehicle counts/predictions and less detailed CNOSSOS sound propagation model	55 dB Lden	Human-centric spectral sensitivity and daily pattern
Railway noise	Near major railway lines outside cities and main lines inside cities	Member state vehicle counts/predictions and less detailed CNOSSOS sound	55 dB Lden	Human centric spectral sensitivity and daily pattern

		propagation model		
Industry	Near industrial areas	Member state identification of major industry/harbours and less detailed CNOSSOS sound propagation model	55 dB Lden	Human-centric spectral sensitivity and daily pattern
Air traffic	Near airports	Airport authority noise maps.	55 dB Lden	Human-centric spectral sensitivity and daily pattern
Mining activities	Meaningful large-scale noise mapping deemed unfeasible.			

2. Sound propagation in natural areas: model selection and input data

2.1 Outdoor sound propagation physics and its modelling

2.1.1 Soil effects

When sound is propagating over the ground, in some frequency range we will experience amplification of sound (in case of constructive interference between a direct and a ground reflected sound path), while at other frequencies, there can be a strong reduction in level (destructive interference). In case of a rigid ground we typically have amplification of sound at most frequencies of relevance. Also here, there will be destructive interference, but at too high frequencies to be of any practical relevance. Above porous grounds such a grassland, this first destructive interference shifts to much lower frequencies, and then this ground effect, often referred to as ground dip, becomes relevant. This might lead to a strong reduction, down to 15 dB relative to free field propagation, in a frequency range down to a few hundreds of Hertz and stretching until about 1 kHz [1].

The type of natural soil is important in this respect. While significant ground effects are yet observed above grass covered ground, most pronounced ground effects typically appear above a mature forest floor [1]. In the latter, the ground dip becomes even deeper, extends to frequencies as low as 100 Hz, and covers a broad frequency range.

2.1.2 Soil effect in case of low receiver height

Ground effects are even stronger when receiver heights are (very) low. Note that in case of road traffic, the source generation positions (exhaust pipe, tyre road contact patch) also appear very close to the surface [2][3], further enhancing the ground effects. In theory, when source and receiver are both exactly on the (soft) surface, sound would disappear in theory following the aforementioned two ray model, except for the ground wave which especially becomes relevant in the lower frequency range [4]. Anyhow, ground effects can be strong at low receiver heights above natural grounds. Given the significance of ground positioned species, a good modelling of this effect is mandatory. Standard and simplified propagation models like ISO96132 [5] and CNOSSOS [6] are not tuned for these very low receiver heights, producing poor predictions.

2.1.3 Terrain effects

Terrain can have significant effects on sound propagation. Behind an elevation in the landscape, an acoustic shadow zone is formed, where sound can only penetrate through diffraction. Especially at high sound frequencies, this leads to significant level drops. Similarly, a receiver positioned in a landscape depression can experience similar strong shielding. At the other hand, receivers positioned on a slope facing a sound source (e.g. a road in a mountain area) will typically experience stronger exposure levels. The exact terrain undulation on the path between source and

receiver must be known when sufficiently detailed predictions are needed. In addition, the exact positioning of both the source and receiver in the undulating path is of high relevance, as an obstacle close to the source or receiver can have much more shielding effect than surface elevation central in such paths.

2.1.4 Soil and terrain effects

Terrain undulations and soft soil effects will interact and enhance each other. Upon diffraction over a terrain element, sound waves will experience (near) grazing incidence, similar to the aforementioned case where a source and receiver are positioned exactly on the (soft) ground. This phenomenon is called "diffraction assisted ground effects" [1].

2.1.5 Meteorological effects

In the atmospheric boundary layer, especially vertical gradients in the horizontal component of the wind speed, and vertical gradients in the air temperature will lead to refraction of sound. Depending on the wind direction and speed, and the actual air temperature lapse, sound exposure levels can be significantly higher or lower [1][7]. At a distance up to several hundreds of meters, observed differences could easily go up to 3040 dB [1][7]. The longer the propagation distance, the stronger such temporal variations in the actual exposure.

Turbulent scattering of sound is another complex, but important propagation factor when making predictions, and especially relevant whenever an acoustic shadow appears such as behind a noise wall/elevation in the landscape, in case of upward refraction, or when deep destructive interferences appear [7]. Typically, shielding effects are then more modest compared to neglecting atmospheric turbulence.

In addition, meteorology impacts air absorption, and depends on air temperature, relative humidity and to a minor extent on ambient atmospheric pressure [8].

2.1.6 Meteorological and soil effect

In case of downward refraction (e.g. due a temperature inversion condition, or in case of downwind sound propagation), sound is able to interact multiple times with the (soft) ground, thus enhancing ground effects and significant level drops [1][7][9]. In contrast, downward refraction over rigid ground will be enhanced as well, leading to much higher exposure levels.

2.1.7 Harmonoise point to point model (HP2P)

The analytical Harmonoise point-to-point model [10] is able to capture most of the complex acoustical propagation phenomena described before, without leading to excessive calculation times. At its origin, treating terrain as a succession of diffraction edges allows a decent modelling of non-flat grounds in combination with soft ground effects. Ground surfaces are modelled as locally reacting with a frequency dependent impedance, allowing discrimination between different

types of natural soils, and allows using databases of detailed ground impedance models and their parameterization.

Meteorological refraction is treated by a conformal mapping approach, where the ground surface is deliberately curved, which has a decent theoretical basis. The linear logarithmical effective sound speed profiles can easily match even more complex atmospheric boundary layers [9].

Another major benefit of HP2P, in contrast to many other propagation models applicable in a noise mapping context, is its ability to work in 1/3 octave bands, which can be seen as an optimum regarding capturing frequency dependent propagation aspects without entailing excessive calculation times when even further refining. This is especially relevant since our main aim is assessing impacts on biodiversity, where frequency dependent hearing sensitivities might be strongly different between species. Common propagation models working in full octave bands [6][8] might not allow such impact assessment.

The model is basically a one-way approach, and reflections on vertical objects directed back to the source cannot be captured. In case of sound propagation in open (natural) fields, this approach does not seem to be a major drawback. Although approach can be developed to simulate such reflections within the same modelling framework, they would become prohibitively expensive with relation to computational cost.

Development of a python implementation

For this work, the Harmonoise point-to-point implementation was transferred from its original C++ implementation (and corresponding .dll) and an older Python 2.4 implementation, to an up-to-date Python 3.x environment. This was required to make the model compatible with current scientific and geospatial libraries, and to enable its use in largescale automated processing workflows. The underlying Harmonoise sound propagation formulation was preserved, while the surrounding data handling, input preparation and output processing were modernised.

The Python 3 implementation allows the HP2P model to be directly coupled with contemporary geospatial tools for handling vector and raster data. Road networks, receiver points, source-receiver cross-sections, elevation profiles and landcover information can therefore be generated and processed within a single workflow. This avoids the need for manual preparation of individual propagation paths and makes it possible to apply the model repeatedly over many tiles and study areas.

A key part of the implementation is the translation of spatial data into the one-dimensional cross section format required by HP2P. For each source-receiver pair, the pipeline samples terrain elevation and landcover classes along the propagation path, simplifies the elevation profile while preserving relevant terrain features, and assigns acoustic ground parameters to the different surface segments. These processed profiles are then passed to the propagation model together with source power, meteorological parameters and receiver configuration.

The resulting implementation therefore acts as a bridge between the analytical Harmonoise model and modern GIS based noise mapping. It keeps the physical basis of HP2P intact but extends its

practical applicability by enabling automated data ingestion, terrain and landcover preprocessing, batch computation, and export of spatially explicit noise map products.

Validation with measurements in complex traffic situation

The HP2P model has been extensively validated in road traffic noise configurations [10]. Of special interest for the current work, is a more recent validation exercise [11] based on long term measurements near a depressed highway, next to a 7m high linear slope consisting of two types of natural soils (rough grassland and sparse forested zone near the top of the slope).

Not only for total A-weighted sound pressure levels the HP2P is very close to both the median of the measurements and a full wave reference model simulation (FDTD) (< 0.5 dBA), but also when comparing simulations and measurements in the detail of 1/3 octave bands (which can be considered as a true validation of the frequency dependent propagation physics involved). The complex ground effect of the mixed ground at the slope is very well reproduced.

Other common noise mapping methods like ISO9613-2, or CNOSSOS, give a poor prediction here, which was already apparent from looking at total A-weighted sound pressure levels. Especially the successful spectral validation is of main interest in the current work, given that specific hearing weighting will be applied.

Figure 1: Validation geometry of the depressed highway case next to a linear slope and mixed ground types. A reference microphone is positioned close to the road edge, a second on the slope.

Figure 2: Sound propagation loss between the two microphones expressed in total A-weighted sound pressure levels. The boxplots show the measurements (over several weeks). Each marker represents a specific modelling effort. (A geo + A atm is a combination of geometrical divergence or distance effect, in combination with atmospheric absorption and neglecting any other propagation feature). From [11].

Figure 3: Sound propagation loss between the two microphones per 1/3 octave band. The boxplots show the measurements (over several weeks). Each coloured line represents different models. [11]

2.2 Data input: elevation maps

Elevation is a critical input to the noise mapping model, as terrain variations strongly influence sound propagation. Based on a scanning of the available data across Europe and a minimal requirement from a sound propagation perspective, the following compromise was reached : (1)

horizontal resolution 2 m; (2) vertical resolution 0.1 m; (3) canopy height of woods, bushes, and other vegetation should not be included in the elevation data.

Digital Terrain Model (DTM) data fulfilling these criteria were sourced from multiple providers depending on the study region:

1. Digital Elevation Model Flanders II – with a spatial resolution of 1m this is available for the Flanders location, Belgium; reference: [link](#) [12]
2. Portugal DTM – Provided at 2 m spatial resolution and accessible via an application programming interface (API), allowing automated download and georeferencing. Reference: [link](#) [13]
3. Spanish DTM – Available at 2 m resolution for the entire country but requiring manual tile based downloads. Reference: [link](#) [14]
4. Additional national and regional DTM datasets may be incorporated where available. Several European countries provide high resolution elevation data, but the access method, tiling system, spatial resolution, vertical reference, licensing conditions and download procedure differ strongly between countries and regions. In many cases, the data are available only through manual tile selection or national geoportals, which makes automated processing over many Natura 2000 regions difficult. Therefore, these datasets are useful for extending the deterministic workflow to additional countries, but they currently require more preprocessing effort than the above mentioned API based datasets offering flexible workflows.

A potentially interesting alternative is to use geospatial data like the one provided by AlphaEarth Foundation to support pan European terrain related data preparation. AlphaEarth provides global 10 m satellite embedding layers in Google Earth Engine, where each pixel is represented by a multidimensional feature vector summarising information from multiple Earth observation sources. These embeddings are not a direct replacement for a bare earth DTM, and they should not be treated as elevation data without validation. However, they may provide useful input features for training a model in regions where high quality DTM data are available, and then transferring this model to regions where direct DTM access is limited or operationally difficult. This could provide a future route for producing consistent terrain related input layers across Europe, but it remains a research option and is not used as the primary elevation source in the current implementation.

2.3 Data input: ground surfaces

Land use and land cover data are obtained from the Dynamic World dataset, a pan European, open access product developed through a collaboration between Google and the World Resources Institute. Dynamic World uses a deep learning model to segment Sentinel2 imagery into nine land cover classes [15]. For each class, distinct acoustic ground properties were then assigned based on the expected acoustic behaviour of porous and acoustically rigid ground surfaces [1][16].

The land cover classes and their assigned acoustic parameters (flow resistivity and porosity) are summarised as follows [1]:

- Water - Flow resistivity: **10000000 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.000000001**
- Trees - Flow resistivity: **20 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.5**
- Grass - Flow resistivity: **300 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.75**
- Crops - Flow resistivity: **200 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.9**
- Shrub and scrub - Flow resistivity: **100 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.45**
- Flooded vegetation - Flow resistivity: **10000000 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.000000001**
- Built-up areas - Flow resistivity: **10000000 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.000000001**
- Bare ground - Flow resistivity: **450 kPas/m²**, Porosity: **0.35**

These parameters are incorporated into the Zwikker and Kosten ground impedance model [16]. The structure factor, the third ground parameter needed in the latter, is commonly approached as the square root of one over porosity [17].

2.4 Data input: meteorological conditions

In the HP2P model, meteorological refraction is represented using linear-logarithmic effective sound speed gradient parameters, while turbulence is represented through a turbulence strength parameter. These quantities are important because wind speed gradients, temperature gradients, and atmospheric turbulence can substantially modify sound propagation, especially over longer source-receiver distances in open natural areas. The earlier physics section already notes that meteorological conditions may strongly increase or decrease sound exposure levels depending on wind direction, wind speed, temperature lapse rate, and turbulence conditions.

For the present implementation, meteorological input parameters are derived from ERA5 reanalysis data [18]. The variables used are the 10 m wind components u_{10} and v_{10} , forecast surface roughness z_0 , friction velocity u_* , soil temperature level 1, used here as an approximation of surface temperature T_{surf} , and surface sensible heat flux $sshf$. Here, u_{10} represents the eastward wind component and v_{10} represents the northward wind component. The accumulated ERA5 sensible heat flux is first converted to an hourly heat-flux rate as

$$Q_H = \frac{sshf}{3600} \quad (1)$$

The heat flux rate is then used to estimate the Monin–Obukhov surface temperature scale T_* , shown in Eq. 2, and the Obukhov length L , shown in Eq. 3. These intermediate quantities describe the stability of the atmospheric surface layer and are required for estimating turbulence related parameters. Temperature variance and temperature length scale are calculated using Eq. 4 and Eq. 5, while velocity variance and velocity length scale are calculated using Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 [19][20][21].

$$T_* = -\frac{Q_H}{u_* \rho_0 c_p} \quad (2)$$

$$L_{MO} = -\frac{u_*^3 T_s \rho_0 c_p}{g \kappa_v Q_H} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_T^2(z) = T_*^2 \left[\frac{4}{(1 + 10(-z/L_{MO}))^{2/3}} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$L_T(z) = 2z \left[\frac{1 + 7(-z/L_{MO})}{1 + 10(-z/L_{MO})} \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma_v^2(z) = 3u_*^2 \quad (6)$$

$$L_v(z) = 1.8z \quad (7)$$

The quantities σ_T^2 and σ_v^2 describe the strength of temperature and velocity fluctuations in the atmospheric surface layer, while L_T and L_v describe the characteristic length scales of these fluctuations. In physical terms, these length scales represent the typical size of turbulent eddies that contribute to scattering of sound. The temperature fluctuations affect the local sound speed, while velocity fluctuations affect the moving medium through which sound propagates. Following the turbulence treatment used in outdoor sound propagation studies [19], these variance and length-scale quantities are converted into Kolmogorov structure parameters, C_T^2 and C_v^2 . These structure parameters provide a compact description of the intensity of temperature and velocity turbulence at acoustically relevant scales. They are then combined into the turbulence strength parameter γ_T , which is used by the propagation model to represent turbulent scattering. Turbulent scattering is important because it can redistribute acoustic energy and partly reduce sharp shadow-zone effects that would otherwise occur under refracting atmospheric conditions.

The corresponding Kolmogorov structure parameters for temperature and velocity are then obtained using Eq. 8 and Eq. 9. These are combined to calculate the turbulence strength parameter γ_T , shown in Eq. 10.

$$C_T^2 = \frac{3\Gamma(5/6)}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\sigma_T^2}{L_T^{2/3}} \quad (8)$$

$$C_v^2 = \frac{3\Gamma(5/6)}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\sigma_v^2}{L_v^{2/3}} \quad (9)$$

$$\gamma_T = \frac{C_T^2}{T_s^2} + \frac{22}{3} \frac{C_v^2}{c_0^2} \quad (10)$$

Wind direction is calculated from the ERA5 wind components using Eq. 11. The resulting angle follows the meteorological convention, meaning that it describes the direction from which the wind is blowing. For each source–receiver cross section, the propagation bearing is calculated from the source and receiver coordinates using Eq. 12. The relative wind angle α , calculated using Eq. 13, then describes the alignment between wind direction and sound propagation direction.

$$\theta_w = \left[\arctan2(u_{10}, v_{10}) \frac{180}{\pi} + 180 \right] \bmod 360 \quad (11)$$

$$\beta = \left[\arctan2(x_r - x_s, y_r - y_s) \frac{180}{\pi} \right] \bmod 360 \quad (12)$$

$$\alpha = [(\theta_w - \beta) \bmod 360] \frac{\pi}{180} \quad (13)$$

This relative angle determines whether the propagation path is approximately downwind, upwind, or crosswind. For example, if sound propagates towards the east, then wind coming from the west corresponds to downwind propagation. Wind coming from the east corresponds to upwind propagation then, while wind coming from the north or south corresponds to crosswind propagation.

The logarithmic and linear effective sound speed gradient parameters are calculated using Eq. 14 and Eq. 15.1 and 15.2, respectively. These equations combine the contribution of wind along the propagation path with the contribution of thermal stratification. In practice, a_{log} controls the logarithmic part of the effective sound speed profile, while a_{lin} controls the linear part. Positive values generally correspond to favourable or downward refracting propagation conditions, whereas negative values correspond to upward refracting conditions.

$$a_{log} = \frac{u_* \cos(\pi - \alpha)}{\kappa} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\gamma_c R_{gas}}{c_0} \left(0.74 \frac{T_*}{\kappa} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$a_{lin}^{day} = \frac{u_* \cos(\pi - \alpha)}{\kappa L} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\gamma_c R_{gas}}{c_0} \left(0.74 \frac{T_*}{\kappa L} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (15.1)$$

$$a_{lin}^{night} = \frac{4.7 u_*}{\kappa L} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\gamma_c R_{gas}}{c_0} \left(4.7 \frac{T_*}{\kappa L} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (15.2)$$

In principle, the above workflow allows meteorological parameters to be calculated separately for each hour and for each source–receiver direction. However, the large-scale deterministic modelling pipeline currently uses one representative meteorological condition for all simulations. This was chosen as a practical simplification, because using fully time and direction dependent meteorology would substantially increase the number of required simulations.

For this implementation, ERA5 data were processed for a spring-morning conditions using 10 years of ERA5 meteorological data. The effective sound-speed gradient parameters a_{lin} and a_{log} were calculated for different source–receiver propagation directions. Rather than modelling every

hourly and directional combination, a representative favourable propagation case was selected. This case corresponds to downwind-like propagation conditions and is derived from the 80th percentile of the spring morning distribution. The turbulence strength γ_T and aerodynamic roughness length z_0 were derived from the same meteorological processing workflow. The figure below shows a_{lin} and a_{log} values for spring morning over 10 years in four different propagation directions.

Figure 4 : Distribution of the computed meteorological slope parameters a_{log} and a_{lin} for spring-morning conditions at 50.50°N , 4.05°E . The location is used here as a fixed reference point for illustrating the meteorological processing workflow and was selected for consistency with the reference location used in previous related work. Values are shown for four sound propagation directions: 0° , 90° , 180° and 270° . The spread of points illustrates the variability in effective sound-speed gradient conditions caused by changes in wind direction, wind speed and atmospheric stability.

Table 2: The final meteorological parameters used in the deterministic noise mapping pipeline are:

Parameter	Description	Value used
a_{lin}	Linear effective sound speed gradient parameter	0.0786 s^{-1}
a_{log}	Logarithmic effective sound speed gradient parameter	0.1048 ms^{-1}
γ_T	Turbulence strength parameter	1.46×10^{-5}
z_0	Aerodynamic roughness length	0.33992 m

3. Road traffic noise mapping

3.1 Open data input for European level modelling

At a national level, road infrastructure information and traffic data is usually available at least for the major roads. However, there is no common standard for making these data openly available across Europe. Hence, we opted for an open data alternative.

Road network data are derived from OpenStreetMap using the Python library OSMnx [22][23]. OSMnx allows road networks to be downloaded as graph based spatial data, where road segments are represented as edges and intersections as nodes. This representation is useful for two reasons: first, it preserves the geometry of the road network required for source-receiver propagation modelling; second, it retains the network connectivity needed for calculating the edge betweenness centrality (see further).

The OpenStreetMap (OSM) “highway” tag is used as the basis for road classification. Roads are grouped into functional categories including motorway, trunk, primary, secondary, tertiary, residential and living streets. Link roads are grouped with their corresponding main class, while unclassified roads are treated together with tertiary roads, as they often represent local connector roads in rural and seminatural areas. This classification provides the basis for assigning traffic related parameters to each road segment.

3.1.1 Road categorization as a proxy for traffic parameters

Traffic count data are not available near all Europe’s natural areas, and therefore traffic parameters must be estimated from open data. In this workflow, road category is used as the first proxy for traffic behaviour. The underlying assumption is that the functional class of a road gives a reasonable indication of its expected traffic volume, vehicle speed and fleet composition, as functional road classification is commonly used to distinguish roads according to their mobility and access roles [24][25].

The OpenStreetMap highway tag is therefore mapped to a limited set of road categories. Higher order roads, such as motorways, trunk roads and primary roads, are assumed to carry larger traffic volumes and higher speeds, while lower order roads, such as residential roads and living streets, are assigned lower baseline values. This does not imply that the assigned traffic values are measured counts; they are used as open databased estimates that allow the Harmonoise/IMAGINE source model to be applied consistently over large spatial extents.

For motorways and trunk roads, the number of lanes is used as an additional proxy for traffic intensity, as described in Section 3.1.2. For primary, secondary, tertiary, residential and living-street classes, a category specific baseline traffic value is used and subsequently refined using edge betweenness centrality, as described in Section 3.1.3.

The numerical traffic parameters used in this section are adapted from the open data traffic estimation procedure which includes the road class baseline traffic values, motorway and trunk

road lane capacity assumptions, hourly saturation factors, edge-betweenness correction parameters, hourly occupancy profiles and heavy vehicle fractions. In that workflow, traffic intensities are estimated from OpenStreetMap road class, lane count and network structure where measured traffic counts are unavailable. The values should therefore be interpreted as generic traffic proxies for large-scale noise mapping, not as observed traffic counts for individual road segments. The same method is adopted here because the objective is to generate spatially complete traffic inputs for Natura 2000 areas across Europe .

Table 3: Road category mapping and baseline traffic parameters used for non – motorway road classes.

Category	OSM highway values	Default speed	Baseline LV intensity before EB scaling	Heavy vehicle fraction
Primary	primary, primary_link	80 km/h	800 veh/h	3%
Secondary	secondary, secondary link	80 km/h	600 veh/h	4-6% depending on hour
Tertiary	tertiary, tertiary link, unclassified	50 km/h	200 veh/h	2%
Residential	residential	30 km/h	70 veh/h	1-2% depending on hour
Living street / service	living street, service	30 km/h	30 veh/h	1-2% depending on hour

The values in Table 3 are baseline traffic values before applying the edge betweenness scaling and hourly occupancy factors. They therefore represent a neutral starting point for each road category. The final hourly light vehicle and heavy vehicle intensities are obtained only after applying the relevant temporal profile and, where applicable, the edge betweenness correction.

This category-based assignment provides the basic traffic input required by the Harmonoise/IMAGINE road source model. For each road segment, the workflow assigns road category, default speed, hourly light vehicle intensity and hourly heavy vehicle intensity. These values are then refined using either number of lanes for motorways and trunk roads, or edge betweenness for the remaining road classes.

3.1.2 Number of lanes as a proxy for traffic intensity on "motorways"

Motorways and trunk roads carry traffic over larger distances across Europe. It is assumed that these roads are designed in a broadly logical way, meaning that the number of lanes and the speed limit are related to the expected traffic volume. For this reason, for "highway = motorway" and "highway = trunk", the number of lanes is used as a secondary parameter to estimate traffic intensity.

For a road segment with one lane, hourly light vehicle intensity is estimated as:

$$LV_h = 0.1 \cdot 1700 \cdot C_{\text{country}} \cdot C_{\text{sat},LV,h} \quad (16)$$

and the corresponding heavy vehicle intensity is:

$$HV_h = LV_h \cdot F_{\text{country}} \cdot F_{HV,h} \quad (17)$$

For a road segment with more than one lane, the light vehicle intensity is estimated using a lane dependent capacity expression:

$$LV_h = (2376 - 95.9 \cdot n_{\text{lanes}}) \cdot n_{\text{lanes}} \cdot C_{\text{country}} \cdot C_{\text{sat},LV,h} \quad (18)$$

$$HV_h = LV_h \cdot F_{\text{country}} \cdot F_{HV,h} \quad (19)$$

where LV_h and HV_h are the hourly light vehicle and heavy vehicle flows, n_{lanes} is the number of lanes, $C_{\text{sat},LV,h}$ is the hourly light vehicle saturation factor, $F_{HV,h}$ is the hourly heavy vehicle fraction, C_{country} is a country specific correction for traffic density, and F_{country} is a country specific correction for heavy vehicle share.

The hourly motorway and trunk road saturation factors are given in Table 4 These values represent the daily traffic pattern used to distribute traffic over the 24 hours of the day.

Table 4: Hourly saturation factor and heavy vehicle fraction for motorway and trunk roads.

Hour	$F_{HV,h}$	$C_{\text{sat},LV,h}$		$F_{HV,h}$	$C_{\text{sat},LV,h}$
0	16%	8.4%	12	18%	40.3%
1	24%	5.5%	13	17%	40.9%
2	32%	4.0%	14	17%	41.2%
3	40%	4.0%	15	16%	43.2%
4	43%	5.8%	16	13%	47.5%
5	39%	12.2%	17	10%	49.5%
6	30%	24.7%	18	10%	44.9%
7	19%	35.9%	19	11%	33.8%
8	15%	38.4%	20	12%	24.4%
9	18%	37.2%	21	12%	19.1%
10	19%	38.6%	22	10%	15.9%
11	18%	39.7%	23	12%	12.0%

For motorway link and trunk link roads, the same approach is used when the link represents a multilane connection between high capacity roads. However, one lane motorway and trunk links are often ramps connecting a motorway to a lower order road. In such cases, the traffic flow is assumed to be substantially lower and is approximated as 10% of the one lane motorway capacity:

$$LVh = 0.1 \cdot 1700 \cdot C_{\text{country}} \cdot C_{\text{sat},LV,h} \quad (20)$$

$$HV_h = LV_h \cdot F_{\text{country}} \cdot F_{HV,h} \quad (21)$$

Country specific correction factors were introduced to account for broad differences in motorway and trunk road traffic density between countries, using values derived from the CEDR 2023 Pan

European Road Network Performance Report [26]. The traffic density correction C_{country} was estimated from the reported average annual daily traffic per lane, using a simple peak hour approximation. The reported AADT/lane value was divided by 10 to approximate a peak hour traffic flow and then normalised by 0.5×1700 veh/h. The heavy vehicle correction F_{country} was estimated by normalising the reported national HGV percentage by a reference value of 16%. These factors are therefore coarse country level corrections, not measured segment level traffic counts. Countries without available data are assigned correction factors equal to 1.

Table 5: Example country level correction factors.

Country code	Traffic density [AADT/lane]	HGV [%]	C_{country}	F_{Country}
AT	11357	12.4	1.3	0.8
BE (F)	14018	16.3	1.6	1.0
BG	—	—	1.0	1.0
CY	—	—	1.0	1.0
CZ	—	—	1.0	1.0
DE	9346	18.4	1.1	1.1
DK	7857	9.3	0.9	0.6
EE	2945	13.2	0.3	0.8
EL/GR	—	—	1.0	1.0
ES	—	—	1.0	1.0
FI	3992	10.4	0.5	0.7
FR	—	—	1.0	1.0
HR	—	—	1.0	1.0
HU	—	—	1.0	1.0
IE	6282	8.5	0.7	0.5
IT	6421	8.8	0.8	0.6
LT	—	—	1.0	1.0
LU	13070	14.2	1.5	0.9
LV	—	23.4	1.0	1.5
MT	—	—	1.0	1.0
NL	13665	15.1	1.6	0.9
PL	—	—	1.0	1.0
PT	—	—	1.0	1.0
RO	—	—	1.0	1.0
SE	4403	14.4	0.5	0.9
SI	8703	14.0	1.0	0.9
SK	—	—	1.0	1.0
Other countries without data	—	—	1.0	1.0

Country codes follow the standard two letter country abbreviations used in European transport datasets. BE (F) denotes Flanders in Belgium. For countries where traffic density or HGV data were not available in the source table, default correction factors equal to 1.0 were used. The table

therefore provides the country level correction factors currently implemented in the workflow, while allowing additional values to be updated when more complete traffic density or heavy vehicle data become available.

3.1.3 Edge betweenness refinement for other roads

For road categories below motorway and trunk level, the number of lanes is often not available, not consistently mapped, or not sufficiently informative. For these roads, the second modelling assumption is used: roads are expected to carry more traffic when they connect more parts of the network. To represent this effect, edge betweenness centrality is used as a network based correction factor.

Edge betweenness quantifies how often a road segment lies on shortest paths between other parts of the road network [27]. Segments with higher edge betweenness values are interpreted as more central to movement through the network and are therefore assigned higher traffic weights than peripheral segments of the same road class. In this workflow, edge betweenness is not treated as a measured traffic count, but as a relative scaling factor applied to the category based traffic estimate.

For primary, secondary, tertiary, residential and living street classes, the edge betweenness correction factor is calculated as:

$$F_{EB} = \max \left(T_{\min}, \min \left(T_{\max}, 1 + (EB - EB_{\text{cross}}) \cdot EB_{\text{slope}} \right) \right) \quad (22)$$

where EB is the edge betweenness of the road segment, EB_{cross} is the category specific crossover value, EB_{slope} controls the sensitivity of the traffic estimate to edge betweenness, and T_{\min} and T_{\max} define lower and upper bounds on the scaling factor. These bounds prevent unrealistically low or high traffic estimates.

Table 6: Edge betweenness correction parameters.

Road category	EB_{cross}	EB_{slope}	T_{\min}	T_{\max}
Primary	2.0×10^6	5.38×10^{-7}	0.01	2.5
Secondary	1.0×10^6	1.08×10^{-6}	0.01	2.5
Tertiary	7.0×10^5	1.54×10^{-6}	0.01	2.5
Residential	1.5×10^5	7.17×10^{-6}	0.01	2.5
Living street / service	1.0×10^5	1.08×10^{-5}	0.01	2.5

The final hourly light vehicle intensity for these road classes is calculated as:

$$LV_h = LV_{\text{base}} \cdot F_{EB} \cdot O_{c,h} \quad (23)$$

where LV_{base} is the category specific baseline value from Table 2 in Section 3.1.1, F_{EB} is the edge betweenness correction factor, and $O_{c,h}$ is the hourly occupancy factor for road category c and hour h .

The corresponding heavy vehicle intensity is then calculated as:

$$HV_h = LV_h \cdot f_{HV,c,h} \quad (24)$$

where $f_{HV,c,h}$ is the category and hour specific heavy vehicle fraction. For oneway roads, the estimated traffic volume is divided by two, because the OSM road segment represents only one direction of travel.

The hourly occupancy factors $O_{c,h}$ and heavy vehicle fractions $f_{HV,c,h}$ used for non-motorway road classes are given in Table 7 and Table 8. These profiles provide generic diurnal traffic patterns for primary, secondary, tertiary, residential and living street roads. They are not measured road segment traffic counts, but category specific temporal profiles used to convert the baseline and edge betweenness scaled traffic estimates into hourly light and heavy vehicle intensities.

Table 7: Hourly light vehicle occupancy factors $O_{c,h}$ for non-motorway road classes.

Hour	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary	Residential	Living/service
0	77	88	63	60	56
1	73	85	56	50	44
2	45	50	31	15	19
3	32	35	25	13	19
4	27	29	19	13	13
5	55	62	19	15	19
6	95	94	81	90	88
7-20	100	100	100	100	100
21	95	97	94	100	100
22	89	94	81	75	75
23	80	91	75	60	50

Table 8: Hourly heavy vehicle fractions $f_{HV,c,h}$ for non-motorway road classes.

Road class	00-06	07	08-21	22	23
Primary	3%	3%	3%	3%	3%
Secondary	4%	4%	6%	5%	4%
Tertiary	2%	2%	2%	2%	2%
Residential	2%	1%	1%	1%	1%
Living street / service	2%	1%	1%	1%	1%

This approach combines three levels of information: the functional road class, the position of the segment within the network, and the expected hourly traffic pattern. The resulting traffic attributed road dataset contains, for each road segment, its geometry, road category, default speed, hourly light vehicle intensity, hourly heavy vehicle intensity, and other attributes required for source power

calculation. This provides a practical open data based representation of traffic inputs for large-scale deterministic noise mapping.

3.2 Source power spectrum

Road traffic source power levels are calculated using the Harmonoise/IMAGINE road vehicle source model [2][10]. The source model separates vehicle noise emission into two physical components: rolling noise, mainly associated with tyre-road interaction, and propulsion noise, associated with the engine, exhaust and transmission. In contrast to the CNOSSOS emission model, the model here is detailed in one third octave bands, allowing using the detailed frequency dependent Harmonoise point-to-point propagation model predictions.

In this workflow, only vehicle category 1 and vehicle category 3 are used. Category 1 represents light vehicles, while category 3 represents heavy vehicles. These two categories are used as the light vehicle and heavy vehicle classes required by the traffic model described in Section 3.1. The source model is applied under default reference conditions: constant vehicle speed, dry reference road surface, and no source directivity corrections.

For each one third octave band i and vehicle category m , the rolling noise sound power level is calculated as:

$$L_{W,R,i,m}(v) = A_{R,i,m} + B_{R,i,m} \log_{10} \left(\frac{v}{v_{\text{ref}}} \right) \quad (25)$$

where $L_{W,R,i,m}$ is the rolling noise sound power level, $A_{R,i,m}$ and $B_{R,i,m}$ are the Harmonoise/IMAGINE rolling noise coefficients, v is the vehicle speed, and $v_{\text{ref}} = 70$ km/h is the reference speed.

The propulsion noise sound power level is calculated as:

$$L_{W,P,i,m}(v) = A_{P,i,m} + B_{P,i,m} \left(\frac{v - v_{\text{ref}}}{v_{\text{ref}}} \right) \quad (26)$$

where $L_{W,P,i,m}$ is the propulsion noise sound power level, and $A_{P,i,m}$ and $B_{P,i,m}$ are the corresponding propulsion noise coefficients.

The total sound power level of a single vehicle of category m in frequency band i is then obtained by energetic summation of the rolling and propulsion components:

$$L_{W,i,m}(v) = 10 \log_{10} \left(10^{L_{W,R,i,m}(v)/10} + 10^{L_{W,P,i,m}(v)/10} \right) \quad (27)$$

where $L_{W,i,m}$ is the total source power level of vehicle category m in frequency band i .

This calculation gives one source power spectrum for light vehicles and one source power spectrum for heavy vehicles. For light vehicles, corresponding to category 1, the source power level is:

$$L_{(W,i,1)}(v) = 10 \log_{10} \left(10^{(L_{(W,R,i,1)}(v)/10)} + 10^{(L_{(W,P,i,1)}(v)/10)} \right) \quad (28)$$

For heavy vehicles, corresponding to category 3, the source power level is:

$$L_{(W,i,3)}(v) = 10 \log_{10} \left(10^{(L_{(W,R,i,3)}(v)/10)} + 10^{(L_{(W,P,i,3)}(v)/10)} \right) \quad (29)$$

For a road segment containing both light and heavy vehicles, the category specific source power levels are combined using the hourly traffic shares of the two vehicle categories. The light vehicle and heavy vehicle shares are defined as:

$$S_{LV} = \frac{Q_{LV}}{Q_{LV} + Q_{HV}} \quad (30)$$

$$S_{HV} = \frac{Q_{HV}}{Q_{LV} + Q_{HV}} \quad (31)$$

where Q_{LV} and Q_{HV} are the hourly light vehicle and heavy vehicle intensities assigned to the road segment.

The mixed source power level for frequency band i is then calculated as:

$$L_{W,i}^{mix} = 10 \log_{10} \left(S_{LV} 10^{(L_{(W,i,1)}/10)} + S_{HV} 10^{(L_{(W,i,3)}/10)} \right) \quad (32)$$

The resulting $L_{W,i}^{mix}$ represents the traffic composition weighted source power spectrum for the road segment under the default source emission assumptions. This frequency dependent source spectrum is subsequently used as input to the deterministic propagation calculation described in Section 3.3.

3.3 Deterministic road traffic noise mapping

To enable scalable processing over large spatial extents, the deterministic road traffic noise mapping is performed tile by tile. The modelling domain is divided into regular 1 km × 1 km tiles, and each tile is treated as an independent processing unit. For each tile, a surrounding 5 km buffer is used to include road segments outside the tile that may still contribute acoustically to receivers inside the tile. This is important in natural areas, where relevant source-receiver distances can extend well beyond the immediate tile boundary, especially for major roads and open propagation conditions.

For each buffered tile, the traffic attributed road network described in Section 3.1 is used as the source dataset. Road segments contain the necessary traffic parameters, including road category, hourly light vehicle and heavy vehicle intensities, vehicle speed and segment geometry. The processing is carried out in the projected coordinate reference system EPSG:3035, which is used consistently for the road network, receiver grid, buffers and source-receiver paths. This ensures that distances and geometric operations are calculated in metres.

Figure 5 : Deterministic road traffic noise mapping workflow from study tile selection to interpolated raster products. The workflow combines open road network data, traffic attribution, receiver point generation, dynamic source-receiver pairing, HP2P propagation and spatial interpolation.

The main deterministic processing settings used in the current implementation are summarised in Table 9. Parameters already defined in earlier sections, such as traffic attribution, source power spectra, ground surface acoustic parameters and meteorological derivation, are not repeated here.

Table 9: Main deterministic noise mapping settings used in the current implementation.

Parameter	Value used	Purpose
Tile size	1 km × 1 km	Independent spatial processing unit
Source / road network buffer	5000 m	Includes acoustically relevant roads around each tile
Working CRS	EPSG:3035	Common projected CRS for distance based processing
Source height	0.03 m	Representative near road source height for road traffic emission
Receiver heights	0.5 m, 5 m, 50 m	Represents near ground, intermediate and elevated biodiversity relevant exposure levels
Distance band increment for thinning	100 m	Distance bands used for adaptive receiver reduction
Removal percentage increment	10 percentage points	Progressive reduction of receiver density with increasing road distance
Major road nearest segment search radius	2500 m	Used for motorway, trunk, primary, secondary and tertiary roads
Minor road nearest segment search radius	500 m	Used for residential, living street and service roads
Dynamic source selection factor	$4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$	Retains additional road segments of the same class around the nearest segment
Elevation simplification tolerance	0.2 m	Douglas-Peucker simplification of sampled elevation profiles
Primary output	Unweighted SPL	Frequency resolved physical output before species specific or A-weighting

Receiver locations are generated from an initial regular candidate grid within each tile. Since sound pressure levels usually show stronger spatial gradients close to roads and smoother variation farther away, a distance adaptive thinning procedure is applied. Receiver points close to acoustically important roads are retained at higher density, while points at increasing distance from the road network are progressively reduced. In the current implementation, distance bands

are evaluated at 100 m increments, and the receiver removal percentage is increased in 10 percentage point steps with distance. The removal percentage assigned to each retained receiver is stored as metadata and is subsequently used to control the level of source selection and cross section construction. In this way, receiver sampling and source-receiver modelling effort are coupled rather than treated as separate steps.

For each retained receiver point, relevant road sources are selected separately for each functional road class. The workflow first searches for the nearest road segment belonging to a given road class. For motorway, trunk, primary, secondary and tertiary roads, the nearest segment search is carried out within a 2500 m radius. For residential, living street and service roads, the search radius is reduced to 500 m, since these roads are expected to have lower traffic intensity and a shorter acoustically relevant range.

Once the nearest segment of a given road class has been identified, the perpendicular distance between the receiver and this nearest segment is calculated. This distance is denoted as d_{perp} . The sources election extent for that road class is then defined as:

$$D_{\text{source}} = 4 \times d_{\text{perp}} \quad (33)$$

All road segments belonging to the same road class and located within this dynamic source selection distance are retained for propagation modelling. Segments belonging to other road classes are handled separately using the same procedure. If no segment of a given road class is found within the relevant nearest segment search radius, that road class is skipped for that receiver. This avoids unnecessary propagation calculations while still allowing spatially important road segments of the same functional class to contribute.

Table 10: Road class specific source selection logic.

Functional road class	Nearest segment search radius	Dynamic source selection rule
Motorway	2500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$
Trunk	2500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$
Primary	2500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$
Secondary	2500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$
Tertiary	2500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$
Residential	500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$
Living street / service	500 m	Retain same class segments within $4 \times d_{\text{perp}}$

Figure 6: The nearest segment is identified using a road class specific search radius, and all same class segments within $4 d_{perp}$ are retained for propagation modelling. The nearest segment is identified using a road class specific search radius, and all same class segments within $4 d_{perp}$ are retained for propagation modelling.

For every retained source segment, a source-receiver cross section is constructed from the segment midpoint to the receiver location. These cross sections represent the two dimensional propagation planes required by the Harmonoise point-to-point model. The use of segment midpoints provides a practical line source discretisation, while the dynamic source selection rule prevents the calculation from including distant road segments that are unlikely to affect the receiver significantly.

Along each cross section, elevation and landcover information are sampled at regular intervals. The elevation profile is then simplified using the Douglas- Peucker line simplification procedure [28], with a tolerance of 0.2 m in the current implementation. This removes redundant intermediate points while retaining terrain features relevant for diffraction and shielding. Landcover transitions are preserved explicitly, because changes in landcover class correspond to changes in acoustic ground impedance. The resulting simplified cross section therefore contains the essential terrain and ground surface information needed for propagation calculation, without keeping every sampled point from the original high resolution profile.

Sound propagation is calculated for each source-receiver cross section using the Harmonoise analytical point-to-point model [10]. The model combines the traffic source power spectra described in Section 3.2 with propagation effects due to geometrical spreading, atmospheric absorption, ground impedance, terrain diffraction, meteorological refraction and turbulence scattering [1][7][10][19]. The implementation uses the same third octave band frequency structure as the source power model, allowing the output to remain fully frequency resolved. This is important because the later biodiversity oriented exposure assessment may require species specific hearing weightings rather than only broadband or A-weighted sound levels.

For each receiver, road segment contributions are combined by energetic, logarithmic summation. Aggregation is first performed over all retained source segments belonging to the same road class, and then across road classes to obtain the total road traffic contribution. For a receiver R , road class c , frequency band f , hour h , and receiver height z , the road class contribution can be written as:

$$L_{p,R,c,f,h,z} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_{s \in S_{R,c}} 10^{L_{p,s,R,f,h,z}/10} \right) \quad (34)$$

where $S_{R,c}$ is the set of retained road segments of road class c for receiver R , and $L_{p,s,R,f,h,z}$ is the sound pressure level contribution from source segment s to receiver R . The total road traffic level at the receiver is then obtained by summing the road class contributions energetically:

$$L_{p,R,f,h,z}^{\text{total}} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_c 10^{L_{p,R,c,f,h,z}/10} \right) \quad (35)$$

The deterministic point output therefore consists of sound pressure levels resolved by frequency band, hour of day, receiver height and road class, together with the total road traffic contribution. In the current implementation, calculations are performed for receiver heights of 0.5 m, 5 m and 50 m. These heights allow exposure to be assessed near the ground, at an intermediate height, and at an elevated height relevant for different animals and ecological applications.

Finally, the discrete receiver point predictions are converted into continuous raster noise maps using spatial interpolation. This interpolation step is required because the receiver grid is intentionally nonuniform after distance adaptive thinning. Interpolation reconstructs a complete spatial noise field over the tile while preserving the computational savings obtained from reducing the number of receiver points. The resulting deterministic maps are stored as georeferenced raster layers and are used both as final analytical outputs and as physically consistent target data for training the machine learning surrogate model.

Overall, this deterministic workflow provides a compromise between physical detail and computational feasibility. The use of Harmonoise preserves the main propagation mechanisms needed in natural areas, while tile based processing, adaptive receiver thinning, dynamic source selection, terrain aware cross section construction and spatial interpolation make it possible to generate training data over many landscapes without running an unnecessarily dense calculation everywhere.

3.4 Machine learnt road traffic noise mapping

The deterministic Harmonoise based workflow described in the previous sections provides physically detailed road traffic noise maps by combining frequency dependent road traffic source power, terrain, ground properties, meteorological conditions and source receiver propagation paths. This level of detail is important for modelling noise exposure in natural areas, where terrain undulation, porous ground surfaces and low receiver heights can strongly influence the resulting sound levels.

However, applying the full deterministic workflow directly to all Natura 2000 areas in Europe would be computationally extremely demanding. Each receiver calculation requires the construction of source-receiver paths, sampling of elevation and landcover data, calculation of frequency dependent propagation effects, and logarithmic aggregation of multiple road segment contributions. Although this approach is suitable for selected training areas, validation studies and physically detailed case studies, it is not practical as the only method for continental scale mapping.

For this reason, a machine learning surrogate modelling strategy is introduced. In this approach, the deterministic Harmonoise model is first used to generate physically consistent road traffic noise maps for representative tiles. These deterministic simulations are then used as training targets for a data driven model that learns the relationship between geospatial input layers and the resulting noise fields. The machine learning model therefore does not replace the physical model conceptually; rather, it approximates its output after being trained on deterministic simulations.

The purpose of the surrogate model is to enable faster prediction over larger spatial extents while retaining sensitivity to the main spatial drivers of road traffic noise propagation. These include the spatial distribution of road sources, frequency dependent source power, terrain variation and acoustically relevant ground properties. The machine learnt maps are therefore intended as a scalable extension of the deterministic modelling framework, with the Harmonoise simulations remaining the physical basis of the training data.

3.4.1 Machine learning strategy

The machine learning strategy treats road traffic noise mapping as a supervised spatial prediction problem. In this setup, the deterministic Harmonoise workflow is used to generate reference sound pressure level maps for selected representative tiles, and these maps are then used as target data for training the surrogate model. The aim is not to replace the deterministic model conceptually, but to learn an efficient approximation of its output for new areas where the same type of geospatial input data are available.

The learning task is formulated as image to image regression. Each training sample consists of a multichannel input raster stack and a corresponding deterministic target stack. The input stack describes the main spatial controls on road traffic noise emission and propagation, including terrain variation, acoustic ground properties and frequency resolved road traffic source power. The target stack contains the 27 frequency resolved sound pressure level layers generated by the deterministic Harmonoise model.

Figure 7: Training strategy for the machine learning surrogate model. The deterministic Harmonoise workflow is first applied to selected representative tiles to generate frequency resolved reference noise maps. The corresponding terrain, ground impedance and road source layers are aligned to a common raster grid and stacked into a multichannel input tensor. The surrogate model is trained to predict the deterministic frequency resolved SPL target maps over the central valid prediction region.

The configuration of the learning problem is summarised in Table 11. This table describes the input and output representation used for the surrogate model, rather than the full internal neural network design.

Table 11: Machine learning surrogate input and output configuration.

Component	Configuration used in the current workflow	Purpose
Input tile size	1000 × 1000 pixels	Provides spatial context around the central prediction area
Prediction / supervision area	Central region of 99 × 99 pixels	Reduces edge effects and ensures training is performed only where deterministic target maps are available
Terrain input	1 channel	Represents local terrain variation relevant to propagation
Ground input	2 channels	Represents real and imaginary components of acoustic ground impedance derived from landcover classes
Light vehicle source input	27 frequency band channels	Provides frequency resolved LV source power information
Heavy vehicle source input	27 frequency band channels	Provides frequency resolved HV source power information
Total input channels	57 channels	Combined multimodal predictor stack
Output layers	27 channels	Frequency resolved SPL target layers
Spatial alignment	Common raster grid	Ensures that terrain, ground, source power and target SPL layers correspond pixel by pixel
Target source	Deterministic Harmonoise simulations	Provides physically consistent reference maps for supervised learning

The configuration in Table 11 summarises the learning problem. Each training sample consists of a multichannel input raster stack and a corresponding deterministic sound level target stack. The input stack combines terrain information, acoustic ground impedance layers and frequency resolved traffic source power rasters. The target stack contains the 27 frequency resolved sound pressure level maps generated by the deterministic Harmonoise model. This structure allows the surrogate model to learn the spatial distribution of road traffic noise while preserving its spectral information, which is required for later biodiversity weighted exposure assessment.

A convolutional neural network based on the U-Net family is used because both the predictors and the outputs are spatially structured [29]. U-Net type models are well suited to dense prediction tasks because they combine an encoder, which extracts spatial context, with a decoder, which reconstructs spatially resolved output maps. Skip connections between the encoder and decoder help preserve spatial detail, which is important for noise mapping because sound levels can change rapidly near roads and terrain features.

In this workflow, the surrogate model follows a two branch U-Net concept. One branch processes the full input tile, allowing the model to retain wider spatial context around the prediction area. A second branch focuses on the central region where deterministic target data are available. Features from both branches are combined before the final prediction step. This design allows the model to account for broader source distribution patterns while also preserving local spatial information close to the prediction region.

Figure 8: Conceptual two branch U-Net architecture used for surrogate road traffic noise mapping. The full context branch processes the complete 1000 × 1000 input tile, while the centre region branch focuses on the central prediction area. Features from both branches are merged and decoded to produce 27 frequency resolved SPL prediction layers. The figure is intended as a conceptual description of the surrogate architecture.

Table 12: Training and validation strategy for the surrogate model.

Component	Configuration / approach	Purpose
Learning task	Supervised image to image regression	Predict spatial SPL fields from geospatial raster inputs
Training targets	Deterministic Harmonoise simulations	Provides physically consistent reference maps
Loss function	Masked mean squared error	Computes error only over valid target pixels
Supervision region	Central region of the tile	Avoids penalising the model outside the deterministic target area
Normalisation	Statistics derived from training data	Improves numerical stability and consistency between layers
Model output	Multiband raster prediction	Produces frequency resolved SPL maps for GIS based postprocessing
Inference workflow	Same raster preprocessing as training	Ensures consistent application to new tiles

Training is carried out using deterministic simulations rather than measured noise maps. This is necessary because measured data with the required spatial coverage, frequency resolution and environmental detail are not available at European scale. The deterministic simulations therefore provide a consistent physical reference dataset from which the surrogate model can learn. During

training, the loss is calculated only over the valid central prediction region, using a binary mask. This avoids learning from pixels where deterministic targets are not available and helps reduce boundary related artefacts. Once trained, the surrogate model can be applied to new tiles using the same preprocessing workflow used during training. The output consists of 27 frequency resolved predicted SPL raster layers. These predicted layers can be assembled across larger regions and later combined with species or taxon specific hearing sensitivity information for biodiversity weighted noise exposure assessment.

3.4.2 Europe's Natura 2000 road traffic noise exposure maps

The following figures present selected examples of the deterministic road traffic noise mapping outputs generated by the HP2P workflow. The results are shown for a limited number of road categories and receiver heights, rather than for every possible road type and height combination, in order to illustrate the main output products without overloading the report. For each selected case, the broadband, unweighted SPL map is presented first, followed by the corresponding frequency resolved SPL maps. The broadband map provides the overall spatial distribution of sound pressure level, while the frequency specific maps show how the predicted noise field varies across the 27 one-third octave bands from 25 Hz to 10 kHz. Together, these figures demonstrate both the final raster noise product and the underlying spectral information required for later biodiversity weighted noise exposure assessment.

Figure 9 : Broadband sound pressure level map for motorway and motorway link type of roads with receiver heights 0.5 m for a Natura2000 region (ID: PTCO0023).

Figure 10 : Frequency specific sound pressure level maps for motorway and motorway link type of roads with receiver heights 0.5 m for a Natura2000 region (ID: PTCO0023)

Figure 11 : Broadband sound pressure level map for Primary and Primary link type of roads with receiver heights 5 m for a Natura2000 region (ID: PTCO023)

Figure 12 : Frequency specific sound pressure level maps for Primary and Primary link type of roads with receiver heights 5 m for a Natura2000 region (ID: PTCO023)

Figure 13 : Broadband sound pressure level map for Tertiary and Tertiary link type of roads with receiver heights 50 m for a Natura2000 region (ID: PTCO023)

Figure 14 Frequency specific sound pressure level maps for Tertiary and Tertiary link type of roads with receiver heights 50 m for a Natura2000 region (ID: PTCO023)

The selected broadband and frequency resolved maps shown above demonstrate the main deterministic road traffic noise products generated by the HP2P workflow. The broadband maps summarise the overall spatial distribution of unweighted SPL, while the frequency resolved maps preserve the spectral structure required for subsequent biodiversity weighted exposure assessment. Although the workflow provides physically detailed road traffic noise maps, applying the full deterministic model over all Natura 2000 areas in Europe is computationally expensive. Each receiver point requires road source selection, source-receiver profile extraction, terrain and land cover sampling, and frequency resolved propagation calculations across 27 one-third octave bands. Therefore, selected study areas were processed first using the Flemish high-performance computing (HPC) infrastructure. Portugal was selected as one of the first test regions because high-resolution elevation data were accessible through an API-based workflow, allowing the terrain input to be integrated efficiently into the modelling pipeline. These deterministic maps provide both example outputs of the workflow and physically consistent reference data for the machine-learning surrogate model. The Portugal example shown below illustrates one such calculated region, consisting of selected 1 km² Natura 2000 study areas, where the deterministic workflow was applied to generate frequency-resolved unweighted SPL maps.

Figure 15: Example deterministic road traffic noise map generated for a few Natura 2000 regions in Portugal. The left panel shows the Natura2000 study areas within Portugal, while the right panel shows the interpolated unweighted Broadband SPL map for tertiary roads at a receiver height of 50 m. This example illustrates the type of physically based HP2P output generated for use as reference data and training samples for the machine learning surrogate workflow.

3.4.2 Machine learnt road traffic noise maps

To illustrate the output of the machine learning surrogate model, this section presents an example prediction for a Natura 2000 study tile in Portugal, PTCON0024(11). The example corresponds to tertiary road traffic noise. The deterministic HP2P result is used as the reference output, while the machine-learnt map is generated from the same type of geospatial input layers used during training, including terrain elevation, acoustic ground properties and frequency resolved road source information.

Figure 16 and Figure 17 below compare the deterministic and machine-learnt frequency resolved SPL maps. The deterministic maps show the physically calculated sound pressure level field for each one-third octave band from 25 Hz to 10 kHz. The predicted maps reproduce the main spatial and spectral patterns of the deterministic output. Higher levels occur close to the road corridor, while lower levels appear in regions affected by distance, terrain shielding and ground related attenuation. The model also captures the overall frequency-dependent behaviour: low and mid frequencies remain more spatially extensive, whereas high-frequency levels decrease more rapidly with distance and shielding.

Figure 16 Deterministic HP2P frequency-resolved SPL maps for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCON0024(11). The panels show one-third octave band sound pressure levels from 25 Hz to 10 kHz using a common SPL colour scale.

Figure 17 Machine learnt frequency resolved SPL maps for the same Natura 2000 site, road class. The surrogate model predicts 27 frequency resolved SPL layers from the geospatial input stack.

The comparison shows that the machine learning surrogate preserves the dominant spatial structure of the deterministic Harmonoise sound propagation solution. In particular, the curved high-level region associated with the tertiary road, the lower level zone in the central-left part of the tile, and the broad transition from high to low SPL across the study area are reproduced.

Figures below show the corresponding non-weighted broadband SPL maps. These broadband maps are obtained by energetic summation of the frequency-resolved SPL layers and are included only as a compact visual summary of the predicted noise field. The broadband comparison confirms that the surrogate model retains the main exposure pattern of the deterministic result, including the higher levels near the road corridor and the lower levels in the acoustically shielded or more distant parts of the tile.

Figure 18 Deterministic broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCON0024(11),

Figure 19 Machine-learnt broadband SPL map for the same polygon as shown in figure 18

This example demonstrates the intended role of the machine learning model in the overall workflow. The deterministic HP2P model remains the physical reference used to generate training data, while the surrogate model provides a faster approximation that can be applied to larger numbers of Natura 2000 tiles. The frequency resolved structure of the output is retained, which is essential for later biodiversity oriented post processing, including species or taxon specific hearing threshold weighting.

3.5 Bio weighted road traffic noise maps

Spectro temporal characteristics of the noise influence the effect on species and eventually biodiversity. Hearing thresholds, mechanisms, and effect thresholds are obtained from WP1. The

way this knowledge is included in the noise model depends on the application of this model (Figure 20). For application in WP2 where European wide correlations between noise and species abundancy targeted, spectral weighting is expected to have little effect because the spread in exposures is so large that the noise level merely indicates that traffic noise is present. For impact assessment in WP3 and for predicting the impact of mitigation in WP5, the specific species that are of interest are known. In that case specific weightings can be applied to combine the noise maps calculated per 1/3 octave band.

Figure 20: positioning of the noise model within the WP structure of the plan B project.

For species using sound as a means of communication, interference could be estimated by considering the communication frequencies of that species. The advantage of such an approach is that vocalisations are available for many species in online databases and can even easily be recorded if no data is available for that (rare) species. This approach has been illustrated in [30]. Since plausible pathways to effects are broader than communication, it was decided to use hearing threshold as a primary weighting. It reflects the minimal condition to trigger possible effects. More details can be found in WP1. To make the hearing threshold weighting (HTw) operational the pipeline shown in Figure 21 is used. To allow estimating HTW for species for which no data is available, the GBIF species ontology (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) is linked to each study that reports hearing thresholds. The HTw together with metadata on the study where these have been derived is stored in a semantic web database using OWL (<https://www.w3.org/>). This standardised language was chosen because of its openness and widely available tools and libraries for accessing it. For easy access, the class hierarchy (species, genus, family, order, class, phylum, kingdom) for each species is duplicated in the HTW web database. Each *HearingThresholdMeasurementCampaign* is treated as an *individual* in the OWL lingua. Unfortunately, OWL does not allow to store lists of tuples (frequency threshold pairs) hence each measurement of a hearing threshold at a given frequency has to be stored as a separate *HearingThresholdMeasurement*. This slight disadvantage is only observable when manually editing the OWL file (e.g. using web protégé). Python scripts are developed to update the hearing threshold web database with data from an excel file or other format and an online viewer is available to visualize and check the data.

The advantage of using the semantic web for this purpose is however that it can be used more broadly by the community, outside plan-B and it can easily be updated as new HT measurements become available.

Figure 21 Flow chart for hearing threshold weighting: in the preparatory phase: (orange), from a database of studies with literature reference and digitized hearing thresholds provided by WP1 a web database is created after including full family tree information from the online species ontology GBIF.. For impact assessment and mitigation, the important taxa can then be identified (blue). If a direct query to the online database does not result in available hearing threshold, the closest taxa can be searched via a combination of GBIF and the available data.

For impact assessment and mitigation prediction, the calculated 1/3 octave band maps are combined after applying the appropriate weighting. For this, the taxa of importance for the region under study first must be selected. With these taxa, the HT web database can be queried. If it is found (subclasses are included in the search) the HT are retrieved, interpolated to 1/3 octave bands, and averaged if multiple measurements are available. If the taxa are not present, the GBIF ontology is used to find the full classification and this classification is used to get the closest related taxa in the HT web database.

To demonstrate the hearing threshold weighted post processing, the frequency resolved tertiary road traffic noise maps for the polygon PTC0N0024(11) were combined using selected species or species group hearing threshold curves. The examples shown here include barn owl, songbird, fox and human hearing thresholds. The human weighted map is included only as a comparison case, while the animal weighted maps illustrate how the same road traffic noise field can be translated into biodiversity relevant exposure layers.

For each species or species group, the hearing threshold curve is first interpolated to the 27 one third octave frequency bands used by the noise model. The frequency specific weighted level is then calculated by comparing the predicted SPL in each band with the corresponding hearing threshold. The weighted broadband map is obtained by energetic summation over the weighted frequency bands. Conceptually, this can be written as:

$$L_{HT,f} = L_{p,f} - HT_f \quad (35)$$

$$L_{HT,broadband} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\sum_f 10^{L_{HT,f}/10} \right) \quad (36)$$

where $L_{p,f}$ is the predicted sound pressure level in frequency band f , HT_f is the interpolated hearing threshold of the selected species or species group, and $L_{HT,broadband}$ is the resulting hearing threshold weighted broadband level. The weighted level should therefore be interpreted as an audibility related exposure indicator for the selected receiver, not as a conventional unweighted physical SPL.

The following figures show the hearing threshold weighted broadband maps for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCO0024(11). Results are shown for different receiver heights depending on the ecological use case. The 0.5 m receiver height represents near ground exposure, relevant for ground dwelling mammals and low height receptors. The 5 m receiver height represents an intermediate exposure height, relevant for animals using shrubs, trees or elevated structures. The 50 m receiver height gives an elevated exposure layer, useful for comparing how the same noise field changes higher above the ground.

The maps preserve the main spatial structure of the original road traffic noise field, with higher weighted levels close to the tertiary road corridor and lower levels in areas affected by distance, terrain shielding and ground related attenuation. However, the final weighted level differs between barn owl, songbird, fox and human examples because each hearing threshold curve gives a different importance to the individual frequency bands. This is why frequency resolved noise modelling is needed for biodiversity applications. A single broadband SPL map would treat all animals in the same way, while the hearing threshold weighted maps produce species or group specific exposure layers. Note that in the figures below, the level scaling is adapted to the specific figure to reveal all possible detail in the maps.

Figure 22 Barn owl hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCON0024(11), receiver height 50 m.

Figure 23 Barn owl hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCO0024(11), receiver height 5 m.

Figure 24 Songbird hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCO0024(11), receiver height 50 m.

Figure 25 Songbird hearing threshold weighted frequency specific SPL maps for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCO0024(11), receiver height 5 m.

Figure 26 Fox hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCO0024(11), receiver height 0.5 m.

Figure 27 Fox hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCO0024(11), receiver height 5 m.

Figure 28 Human hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCON0024(11), receiver height 50 m.

Figure 29 : Human hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in Natura 2000 site PTCON0024(11), receiver height 5 m.

Figure 30 : Human hearing threshold weighted broadband SPL map for tertiary road traffic noise in site PTCO0024(11), receiver height 0.5 m.

4. Wind turbine noise mapping

Wind turbine noise is modelled as a second source category within the same deterministic Harmonoise point-to-point framework used for road traffic noise mapping. The main difference is the source representation. Whereas road traffic noise is modelled as a set of road segments with traffic dependent source power, wind turbines are represented as elevated point sources located at their mapped turbine positions. The propagation calculation itself remains based on source receiver cross sections, terrain sampling, land cover derived ground impedance, and ERA5 derived meteorological parameters.

This section describes the wind turbine noise mapping workflow. It includes the source power representation, the extraction and filtering of wind turbine locations near Natura 2000 areas, and the deterministic calculation of turbine noise maps.

4.1 Source power level modelling

Wind turbine source emission is represented using a sound power spectrum. In the current implementation, a reference turbine source power spectrum is used, defined in one third octave frequency bands from 25 Hz to 10 kHz. The source spectrum is taken from the Belle River Wind Power Project Turbine T44 IEC 6140011 Edition 3.0 measurement report [31]. The turbine reported is a Siemens Gamesa SWT 2.473113 with a hub height of 99.5 m, and the spectrum is based on Appendix C, Table C.01, “Detailed apparent sound power level data at hub height”.

Each turbine is treated as an elevated point source. The source height is represented by the turbine hub height. Where hub height information is available in the turbine dataset, it can be read from available turbine attributes. Where this information is missing or uncertain, a set of representative hub heights is used. In this workflow, four hub height scenarios are considered: 80 m, 90 m, 100 m and 110 m.

The frequency dependent point source level at a receiver is then calculated by combining the turbine source power spectrum with the Harmonoise propagation attenuation along the source receiver path. For a turbine j , frequency band i , and receiver r , this can be written conceptually as:

$$L_{p,i,j}(r) = L_{W,i,j} - A_{tot,i,j}(r)$$

where $L_{W,i,j}$ is the turbine source power level in frequency band i , and $A_{tot,i,j}(r)$ is the total frequency dependent propagation attenuation between the turbine and receiver. The attenuation term includes the same physical propagation effects used in the deterministic Harmonoise workflow, including geometrical spreading, ground interaction, terrain related diffraction and meteorological effects.

4.2 Data input: Europe’s wind turbine spots

Wind turbine locations are derived from OpenStreetMap [22] again using OSMNx as explained in the road data download section 3.1. Turbines are extracted as generator features where the source

is tagged as wind. The extraction is performed country by country using European country boundaries, and the resulting turbine points are merged into a common European wind turbine dataset. The workflow also stores country identifiers and available turbine metadata, including fields such as name, operator, power, generator type, model, total height, hub height and rotor diameter where available [23].

The wind turbine dataset is then filtered spatially to identify turbines relevant for Natura 2000 exposure assessment. Candidate turbines are intersected with buffered Natura 2000 geometries stored in the project database. The filtering script uses the Natura 2000 geometry table in EPSG:3035 and applies the configured buffer distance of 1 km around Natura 2000 features before selecting intersecting turbines.

Table 13: Wind turbine input data configuration.

Component	Configuration / source	Purpose
Turbine locations	OpenStreetMap wind generator features	Provides European wind turbine point locations
Natura 2000 selection	Spatial filtering using buffered Natura 2000 geometries	Selects turbines relevant for protected area exposure
Modelling projection	EPSG:3035	Provides a common European projected coordinate system
Elevation input	Regional or national elevation raster	Provides terrain profile along turbine-receiver paths
Landcover input	Dynamic World landcover raster	Provides acoustic ground property classes
Meteorology input	ERA5derived Harmonoise parameter raster	Provides a_{lin} , a_{log} , γ_T and z_0 at turbine locations
Hub height scenarios	80, 90, 100 and 110 m	Represents uncertainty or variability in turbine source height

4.3 Deterministic wind turbine noise mapping

The deterministic wind turbine noise mapping uses the same Harmonoise point-to-point propagation implementation as the road traffic workflow. For each turbine, a receiver grid is generated around the turbine location. In the current configuration, receivers are created on a 10 m grid within a square area around the turbine, with a small void radius around the source to avoid unrealistically short source receiver distances. Distance based thinning is then applied so that receiver density is highest close to the turbine and progressively reduced farther away.

For each source receiver pair, a straight propagation path is constructed from the turbine hub position to the receiver. Elevation and land cover values are sampled along this path at 1 m spacing, and the elevation profile is simplified using the same profile simplification setting used in the earlier deterministic workflow. The sampled land cover classes are converted into acoustic ground parameters using the same flow resistivity and porosity values as the road traffic noise calculations.

Meteorological propagation parameters are sampled from the ERA5 derived Harmonoise meteorological raster at the turbine location. The raster provides the representative a_{lin} , a_{log} , γ_T and z_0 values used by the propagation model. The workflow samples these bands for each turbine and inserts them into the turbine specific propagation configuration before running the deterministic calculation.

The ERA5 meteorological raster is derived from spring morning conditions over the 2014–2023 period. The processing uses March, April and May, the 06:00–09:00 time window, the 80th percentile statistic, and four representative propagation directions. The output includes $a_{log,p80}$, $a_{lin,p80}$, $\gamma_{T,p80}$, z_0 , and directionspecific a_{log} and a_{lin} fields.

The deterministic calculation is repeated for the selected hub height scenarios and receiver height scenarios. The current configuration includes hub heights of 80, 90, 100 and 110 m, and receiver heights of 0.5 m, 5 m and 50 m.

The computed point results are converted into raster maps using a 10 m output grid. The rasterization step uses nearest neighbour interpolation from the calculated receiver points, with a fixed search radius and a defined number of neighbouring points. Both overall SPL rasters and frequency resolved SPL rasters can be exported.

Table 14: Deterministic wind turbine noise mapping configuration.

Component	Configuration used	Purpose
Source type	Elevated point source	Represents the turbine nacelle / hub position
Hub-height scenarios	80, 90, 100 and 110 m	Represents turbine-height variability
Receiver heights	0.5, 5 and 50 m	Supports near-ground and elevated exposure assessment
Receiver spacing	10 m	Defines the base receiver grid resolution
Receiver domain	1 km × 1 km around each turbine	Captures local turbine noise exposure around the source
Receiver thinning	Distance-based thinning	Reduces computation while retaining detail near the source
Cross-section sampling	1 m interval	Samples terrain and land cover along source–receiver paths
Elevation simplification	$\epsilon = 0.2$ m	Reduces terrain-profile complexity while preserving relevant shape
Output raster size	10 m pixels	Produces GIS-compatible wind turbine noise maps
Meteorology	ERA5 spring-morning P80 parameters	Represents favourable propagation conditions

4.4 Wind turbine noise maps

The deterministic wind turbine noise maps are produced for selected turbine locations, within and around a buffered distance of 1 km of Natura 2000 regions, using the HP2P propagation model. Each turbine is represented as an elevated point source, and simulations are carried out for different hub-height and receiver-height configurations. The resulting receiver-point SPL values are interpolated to continuous raster maps. The examples below show the main output products generated by this workflow: broadband unweighted SPL maps and the corresponding frequency-resolved SPL maps. The broadband maps provide a compact representation of the overall predicted noise field, while the frequency resolved maps preserve the spectral structure of the turbine noise and are therefore suitable for subsequent biological weighting.

Figure 31 Wind Turbine Broadband Sound Pressure Level map for receiver height 0.5 m (Location Flanders, Belgium)

Figure 32 Wind Turbine Frequency specific Sound Pressure Level maps for receiver height 0.5 m (Location Flanders, Belgium)

Figure 33 Wind Turbine Broadband Sound Pressure Level map for receiver height 5 m (Location Flanders, Belgium)

Figure 34 Wind Turbine Frequency specific Sound Pressure Level maps for receiver height 5 m (Location Flanders, Belgium)

Figure 35 Wind Turbine Broadband Sound Pressure Level map for receiver height 50 m (Location Flanders, Belgium)

Figure 36 : Wind turbine frequency specific Sound Pressure Level maps for receiver height 50 m (Location Flanders, Belgium).

The examples shown in this section demonstrate the main deterministic wind turbine noise products generated by the workflow. The broadband SPL maps provide a compact overview of the spatial decay of turbine noise around each source, while the frequency resolved maps show the spectral structure of the predicted sound field. This spectral information is important because different animal groups are sensitive to different frequency ranges. Therefore, the frequency-resolved turbine noise maps provide the necessary basis for subsequent biodiversity weighted noise exposure assessment.

The single turbine examples shown above illustrate the local deterministic sound field around an individual wind turbine. In addition, the workflow has been applied to selected wind turbine regions in Flanders, Belgium, as shown below, and will be extended to compute turbine noise fields across Europe, particularly for turbines located within or near Natura 2000 areas. In contrast to the road traffic workflow, the deterministic HP2P approach can be applied directly for wind turbine noise mapping because the calculations are computationally less demanding. This is mainly because each turbine is represented as an elevated point source, rather than as a dense network of line source segments. The Flanders example below shows the type of regional wind turbine noise layer produced by assembling the deterministic broadband SPL fields around the calculated turbine locations. Where turbines are located close to each other, their contributions are combined energetically to represent cumulative exposure. This is supported by a grid generation strategy that identifies nearby turbines and creates a shared receiver grid around turbine clusters, avoiding unnecessary repeated calculations while still preserving the spatial detail needed near the sources.

Figure 37 : Example of calculated deterministic wind turbine broadband SPL fields in Flanders, Belgium, for hub height 80 m and receiver height 5 m. The left panel shows the selected wind turbine locations, while the right panel shows the corresponding broadband SPL fields produced using the HP2P point source workflow. Where turbines are closely spaced, their contributions are combined energetically to represent cumulative exposure.

5. Intersecting the EC noise map contours with natural ground use

5.1. Methodology

To complement the detailed noise mapping in the EU Natura 2000 zones, an alternative set of noise maps is produced taking the EC reported Lden maps as input. A main advantage of these maps is that the bookkeeping with relation to the passages of cars, trains, and airplanes, and the presence of major industry (including harbours), is implicitly included in these maps. It is assumed that this is done accurately by each member states with knowledge of the local situations. Such essential input data is not open and would be far from being harmonized across the EU, but still is an essential starting point for any noise mapping.

In view of the Environmental Noise Directive, noise contours have to be reported from 55 dB Lden on. In addition to the important task of source identification, propagation modelling is another important pillar of a noise map. Given the use of the CNOSSOS sound propagation model, specific challenges in natural areas are not captured. In brief, this means receiver heights at bedroom window (4 m above the ground), so not capturing the specific propagation physics near the ground, where ground effects, terrain undulation and meteorological refraction have a strong impact (see Chapter 2). In addition, these maps are human-centric: they use A-weighting and rely on the typical human day-evening-night pattern, where evening and night periods are penalized given their stronger impact on a person's health and wellbeing. Full spatial coverage is not reached as contours only start from 55 dB Lden.

In line with the identified misalignments of using the EC noise mapping data for terrestrial biodiversity research, a coarse binary procedure is used here. Zones defined by contours exceeding 55 dB Lden can be considered as zones with *significant* environmental noise, while zones below 55 dB Lden can be designated as *non-significant* noise exposed. This binary reduction allows drawing meaningful conclusions from these maps, without inducing the risk of overly analysing non-fully suited data, and consequently, misinterpretations.

5.2. The 500 m raster maps

To allow linking noise exposure with species abundance based on the EC noise maps (exposure to road traffic, railways, airports, and industry), a binary noise exposure map is produced on a 500 m grid. Two variants were produced:

- In each cell, it can be logically assumed that if species are present, they will be located in zones with a natural ground use. Therefore, the CORINE classification (2018, 100 m resolution) has been used, and natural zones are identified by codes starting at 200 (so including “agricultural zones”, “forest and semi-natural areas”, “wetlands and waterbodies”, excluding “artificial surfaces”). In case of specific interest in species appearing in particular natural zones, this analysis can be easily refined. For the sake of presenting the method,

all natural ground use classes were used. The fraction of noise contours intersecting with such natural ground use is then defined per cell (using the same 100 m resolution). A fraction equal to zero could mean that there is no natural ground use in the cell, or there are no noise contours (exceeding 55 dB), or no intersection between natural ground and noise contours. High noise exposure in case of predominately artificial land is not considered here. A fraction equal to one would mean that the whole cell has natural ground use and fully falls within 55 dB contours. A fraction of 0.5 could mean e.g. that 50 % of the zone has natural land use and 100 % of the surface of the cell falls within a 55 dB noise contour, or e.g. 50 % falls within a noise contour and 100 % of the zone is natural.

- As a complement, a merging of only the noise contours is made, and thus shows the fraction of the surface of the cell having noise exposure above 55 dB, for at least one of the identified noise sources (road, rail, airport, industry), regardless of (natural) ground use.

As an example of the processing and intermediate steps, the case of Belgium is shown in Figure 38. The noise contour mask map clearly shows the big agglomerations, major rail and railway infrastructure, and the harbour zones of Zeebrugge, Antwerp and Ghent. The CORINE land use map depicts the urbanized zones. Their intersection in Figure 39 shows that in the centres of the bigger cities (e.g. Brussels, Ghent, Antwerp), this fraction typically goes to zero, while in their outskirts, fractions reach a value of 1.

Figure 38 Intermediate steps during processing to the 500 m raster fraction maps for Belgium (as an example). On the left, the noise mask is shown (green = inside noise contours, red= outside noise contours). On the right, the land use classification is depicted

Figure 39 Fraction of the natural land use classes intersecting L_{den} contour(s) on a 500 m grid for the country of Belgium.

The full European maps are shown in Figure 40. Note that these maps fully rely on external data, and not all countries provided their noise contours. Even in individual countries, a closer inspection revealed that some regions are missing. It was observed e.g. that for Barcelona in Spain, only an airport noise contour map was available. As discussed before, a similar European map is provided

in Figure 41, where natural ground use was not considered. Notwithstanding these limitations, the current European map provides a near full coverage for broad non-detailed assessment of the link between species abundance and anthropogenic noise exposure.

Figure 40 : Fraction of natural land use classes intersecting Lden contour(s) on a 500 m grid for the EU. For Slovenia, Slovakia, Greece, Bulgaria and Hungary, noise maps were not available, while nonEU countries Switzerland and Norway are included. Oversea territories, except for Mediterranean islands, were not considered.

Figure 41: Fraction of the noise contours within a 500 m grid for the EU. For Slovenia, Slovakia, Greece, Bulgaria and Hungary, noise maps were not available, while non-EU countries Switzerland and Norway are included. Oversea territories, except for Mediterranean ones, were not considered.

6. Conclusions

The project delivers four complementary noise mapping products and frameworks : (1) deterministic high-resolution road traffic noise maps for selected case-study areas, (2) machine learning-based road traffic noise maps covering Natura 2000 sites across the whole of Europe, (3) deterministic wind turbine noise maps at continental scale for each registered turbine, and in addition, (4) END-based binary exposure maps providing a practical means to assess broader environmental noise exposures from railway, air traffic and industrial sources. Together, these datasets establish an adaptable and robust foundation for evaluating the impacts of anthropogenic noise on European biodiversity.

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References

- [1] K. Attenborough and T. Van Renterghem, Predicting Outdoor Sound, 2nd ed. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780429470806>.
- [2] H. G. Jonasson, "Acoustical source modelling of road vehicles," Acta Acustica united with Acustica, vol. 93, no. 2, pp. 173–184, 2007.
- [3] U. Sandberg and J. A. Ejsmont, Tyre/Road Noise Reference Book. Kisa, Sweden: Informex, 2002.
- [4] T. F. W. Embleton, "Tutorial on sound propagation outdoors," Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, vol. 100, no. 1, pp. 31–48, 1996. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.415879>.
- [5] ISO 9613-2:1996, Acoustics — Attenuation of sound during propagation outdoors — Part 2: General method of calculation. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 1996.
- [6] S. Kefalopoulos, M. Paviotti, and F. Anfosso-Lédée, Common Noise Assessment Methods in Europe (CNOSSOS-EU), EUR 25379 EN. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.2788/31776>.
- [7] E. M. Salomons, Computational Atmospheric Acoustics. Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-010-0660-6>.
- [8] ISO 9613-1:1993, Acoustics — Attenuation of sound during propagation outdoors — Part 1: Calculation of the absorption of sound by the atmosphere. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 1993.
- [9] T. Van Renterghem and D. Botteldooren, "Variability due to short-distance favourable sound propagation and its consequences for immission assessment," Journal of the

- Acoustical Society of America, vol. 143, no. 6, pp. 3406–3417, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.5040483>.
- [10] D. van Maercke and J. Defrance, “Development of an analytical model for outdoor sound propagation within the Harmonoise project,” *Acta Acustica united with Acustica*, vol. 93, no. 2, pp. 201–212, 2007.
- [11] T. Van Renterghem and D. Botteldooren, “Landscaping for road traffic noise abatement: Model validation,” *Environmental Modelling & Software*, vol. 109, pp. 17–31, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.08.012>.
- [12] Digitaal Vlaanderen, Digitaal Hoogtemodel Vlaanderen II, DTM, raster, 1 m, 2026. Available: <https://www.vlaanderen.be/datavindplaats/catalogus/digitaal-hoogtemodel-vlaanderen-ii-dtm-raster-1m>. Accessed: 22 May 2026.
- [13] Direção-Geral do Território, LiDAR — Modelos Digitais do Relevo, 2026. Available: <https://cdd.dgterritorio.gov.pt/dgt-fe/catalogos/colecoes>. Accessed: 22 May 2026.
- [14] Instituto Geográfico Nacional, MDT02 — Modelo Digital del Terreno 2 m, Centro de Descargas del CNIG, 2026. Available: <https://centrodedescargas.cnig.es>. Accessed: 22 May 2026.
- [15] C. F. Brown, S. P. Brumby, B. Guzder-Williams, T. Birch, S. B. Hyde, J. Mazzariello, W. Czerwinski, V. J. Pasquarella, R. Haertel, S. Ilyushchenko, K. Schwehr, M. Weisse, F. Stolle, O. Hanson, O. Guinan, R. Moore, and A. M. Tait, “Dynamic World, near real-time global 10 m land use land cover mapping,” *Scientific Data*, vol. 9, 251, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01307-4>.
- [16] C. Zwikker and C. W. Kosten, *Sound Absorbing Materials*. New York: Elsevier, 1949.
- [17] K. Attenborough, I. Bashir, and S. Taherzadeh, “Outdoor ground impedance models,” *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 129, no. 5, pp. 2806–2819, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.3569740>.
- [18] H. Hersbach, B. Bell, P. Berrisford, S. Hirahara, A. Horányi, J. Muñoz-Sabater, J. Nicolas, C. Peubey, R. Radu, D. Schepers, A. Simmons, C. Soci, S. Abdalla, X. Abellan, G. Balsamo, P. Bechtold, G. Biavati, J. Bidlot, M. Bonavita, G. De Chiara, P. Dahlgren, D. Dee, M. Diamantakis, R. Dragani, J. Flemming, R. Forbes, M. Fuentes, A. Geer, L. Haimberger, S. Healy, R. Hogan, E. Hólm, M. Janisková, S. Keeley, P. Laloyaux, P. Lopez, C. Lupu, G. Radnoti, P. de Rosnay, I. Rozum, F. Vamborg, S. Villaume, and J.-N. Thépaut, “The ERA5 global reanalysis,” *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, vol. 146, pp. 1999–2049, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>.
- [19] T. Van Renterghem, K. V. Horoshenkov, J. A. Parry, and D. P. Williams, “Statistical analysis of sound level predictions in refracting and turbulent atmospheres,” *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 185, 108426, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2021.108426>.
- [20] V. E. Ostashev and D. K. Wilson, *Acoustics in Moving Inhomogeneous Media*, 2nd ed. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press, 2016.
- [21] J. Forssén, “Influence of atmospheric turbulence on sound reduction by a thin, hard screen: A parameter study using the sound scattering cross-section,” in *Proceedings of the Long Range Sound Propagation Symposium*, Jackson, USA, 1998.
- [22] OpenStreetMap contributors, OpenStreetMap, 2026. Available: <https://www.openstreetmap.org>. Accessed: 22 May 2026.
- [23] G. Boeing, “Modeling and analyzing urban networks and amenities with OSMnx,” *Geographical Analysis*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 567–577, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gean.70009>.

- [24] European Commission, Road Classification, European Road Safety Observatory, 2006. Available: https://road-safety.transport.ec.europa.eu/european-road-safety-observatory/statistics-and-analysis-archive/roads/road-classification_en. Accessed: 22 May 2026.
- [25] Federal Highway Administration, Highway Functional Classification: Concepts, Criteria and Procedures. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Transportation, Federal Highway Administration, 2013..
- [26] Conference of European Directors of Roads, 2023 Pan-European Road Network Performance Report. CEDR, 2024. Available: <https://horizoneuropencppportal.eu/sites/default/files/2024-12/cedr-2023-pan-european-road-network-performance-report-2024.pdf>. Accessed: 22 May 2026.
- [27] L. C. Freeman, “A set of measures of centrality based on betweenness,” *Sociometry*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 35–41, 1977.
- [28] D. H. Douglas and T. K. Peucker, “Algorithms for the reduction of the number of points required to represent a digitized line or its caricature,” *The Canadian Cartographer*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 112–122, 1973.
- [29] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, “U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation,” in *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention – MICCAI 2015*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 9351, pp. 234–241, 2015.
- [30] D. Botteldooren, T. Van Renterghem, M. Wood, D. Waddington, B. Davies, C. Palhares Teixeira, and R. Klenke, “Sound communication interference weighting for terrestrial animals,” in *Proceedings of the 11th Convention of the European Acoustics Association, Forum Acusticum / Eurnoise 2025*, pp. 257–261.
- [31] Aercoustics Engineering Limited, Belle River Wind Power Project – Turbine T44 – IEC 61400-11 Edition 3.0 Measurement Report. Report ID: 17095.01.T44.RP3. Prepared for Belle River Wind LP. Revision 3, 20 September 2019.